

Base Adduct of Bis (Chloro Acetyl Acetonato) Copper(II) with Nitrogen Donors

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Three green crystalline base adduct having the general formula $[\text{Cu}(\text{Cl-ac.ac})_2\text{L}]$ where Cl-ac.ac is the chloro-acetyl acetone anion and L is nitrogen ligand like quinoline, isoquinoline and beta-picoline, have been synthesized. These were characterised on the basis of analysis, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, i.r. and electronic spectral data are presumably penta-coordinated.

BONDING of additional ligands along the axis normal to the molecular plane of planar complexes has invoked interest in recent years. Spectral evidence is available¹ for the coordination of heterocyclic bases to the planar molecule of bis-(acetyl acetonato) copper(II) and 1:1 adducts of this complex with 4-methyl pyridine and quinoline have been isolated^{2,3}, the base is lost very readily. We have been trying for the adduct formation of metal beta-diketonates with heterocyclic bases and isolated^{4,5} a number of penta-coordinated adducts of zinc(II) beta-diketonates with heterocyclic amines. A quinoline adduct of bis(benzoyl acetonato) copper(II) has been reported⁶. Stability of acetylacetonates has been partly explained on the basis of benzenoid resonance⁷ and reactions characteristic of aromatic system have been carried out⁸⁻¹⁰ on metal acetylacetonates to provide further evidence regarding aromaticity. It was, therefore, thought worthwhile to study the adduct formations of gamma-substituted beta-diketonates and as a part of this investigation a quinoline adduct of bis(nitroacetyl acetonato) copper(II) has been described¹¹. This communication describes three green crystalline 1:1 base (quinoline, isoquinoline, beta-picoline) adducts of bis (chloroacetylacetonato) copper(II).

Experimental

Bis(chloro acetylacetonato) copper(II) was prepared by reacting a methanolic solution of the chelate with dry chlorine gas, and by cooling the reaction mixture in an ice bath. The green compound separated was filtered under suction, washed with methanol, followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*. Analysis of the compound indicated the composition $[\text{Cu}(\text{Cl-ac.ac})_2]$. I.R. spectra provided evidence for the formation of chloro chelate.

The chelate was dissolved in the respective bases by warming till a saturated solution was obtained. The solution was cooled in ice-bath when green crystalline compounds separated out. Excess of the base was driven out by suction and by keeping in a vacuum desiccator containing paraffin.

Composition of the compounds was established by analysing metal, nitrogen and halogen. $[\text{Cu}(\text{Cl-ac.ac})_2\text{L}]$ where L is quinoline and isoquinoline requires, Cu = 19.55, N = 4.31, Cl = 10.92; Found : Cu = 19.32, 19.20; N = 4.1, 4.3; Cl = 10.65, 10.68 respectively. For L = beta-picoline, requires Cu = 21.92, N = 4.83, Cl = 12.24. Found Cu = 21.65, N = 4.58, Cl = 11.92. Conductance was measured in 0.001M acetone solution. Magnetic susceptibility measurement was made on solid specimen using Gouy method. I.R. spectra were recorded on nujol mulls using Unicam SP 200 and Perkin-Elmer 5100 spectrometer. Electronic spectra was recorded in 0.01M chloroform-base solution using Unicam SP500 spectrometer. Spectral data are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE I

Compound	Infrared spectra (cm ⁻¹)				
	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{Cl})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$
$\text{Cu}(\text{ac.ac})_2$	1590	1555	—	440	—
$\text{Cu}(\text{Cl-ac.ac})_2$	1565	1545	1090	440	—
$[\text{Cu}(\text{Cl-ac.ac})_2\text{Q}]$	1570	1555	1090	430	320
$[\text{Cu}(\text{Cl-ac.ac})_2\text{I.Q.}]$	1575	1560	1085	425	320
$[\text{Cu}(\text{Cl-ac.ac})_2\beta\text{-pic}]$	1580	1560	1090	430	325

Compound	Electronic spectra	
	$\nu_{\text{max}}(\text{nm})$	(ϵ)
$\text{Cu}(\text{Cl-ac.ac})_2$	660	100
$[\text{Cu}(\text{Cl-ac.ac})_2\text{Q}]$	650	130
$[\text{Cu}(\text{Cl-ac.ac})_2\text{I.Q.}]$	640	125
$[\text{Cu}(\text{Cl-ac.ac})_2\beta\text{-pic}]$	650	120

Q = Quinoline, I.Q. = Isoquinoline, $\beta\text{-pic}$ = beta-picoline.

Results and Discussion

Analysis of the green crystalline compounds correspond to the composition $[\text{Cu}(\text{Cl-ac.ac})_2\text{L}]$ where L is quinoline, isoquinoline and beta-picoline. The low conductance values (8, 11 and 12 mhos) in acetone are indicative of the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. Magnetic measurement show the complexes to be paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.82, 1.84$ and

1.78 B.M. respectively) with the presence of one unpaired electron.

Infrared spectra of the chelate, chlorochelate and the base adduct are given in Table 1. It is seen that the C-C and C-O stretching frequency of the chelate decreases to a lower frequency and the bands due to C-H stretching and bending vibrations disappear on chlorination. The extent of decrease in frequency is more in case of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$. Disappearance of bands due to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$ at 3000 cm^{-1} and $\delta(\text{C}-\text{H})$ around 1200 cm^{-1} and appearance of a new band around 1090 cm^{-1} attributable to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{Cl})$ provides evidence for chlorination of the chelate. The spectra of the base adduct is complicated for assignment, but most of the bands due to the base are shifted indicating bonding of the nitrogen donor ligand, the information only being obtained by the finger print technique. Concrete evidence for bonding of the base is however, obtained from the shift of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ to higher frequency region in the base adducts and bands attributable to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ around 430 and 320 cm^{-1} respectively in the far-infrared spectrum of the adduct. This has been further substantiated by the observation that the chloro chelate absorbs moisture when left exposed to air and forms $[\text{Cu}(\text{Cl}-\text{ac.ac})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$, the presence of water being identified by analysis and an absorption band at 3450 cm^{-1} in the i.r. spectrum.

$\text{Cu}(\text{ac.ac})_2$ gives rise to high intensity band at 245 nm ($\epsilon = 20,000$) whereas in the chlorochelate the band shifts to the longer wavelength region, i.e., 268 nm ($\epsilon = 11,000$) as the halogenation results in the increase of pi-electron delocalisation in the ring, thereby extending conjugation.

A single broad absorption band is observed for $[\text{Cu}(\text{Cl}-\text{ac.ac})_2\text{L}]$ around 650 nm ($\epsilon = 130$) in the visible region whereas in case of the chloro chelate the band is around 660 nm ($\epsilon = 100$). Though the band does not shift much on coordination with the base there is an increase in the extinction coefficient. Gillard and Wilkinson³ have studied the absorption spectra of $\text{Cu}(\text{ac.ac})_2$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{ac.ac})_2\text{Q}]$ in dichloromethane and reported bands at 658 nm ($\epsilon = 41$)

for the former and 650 nm ($\epsilon = 71$) for the latter compound. Shigmatsu¹² *et al* have observed the λ_{max} for $[\text{Cu}(\text{ac.ac})_2\text{py}]$ at 660 nm in benzene, acetone and chloroform solutions. Graddon¹³ has also observed that there is an increase in the extinction coefficient of the mono adducts of copper(II) beta-diketonates without much shift in the absorption maxima.

Hence the compound under report is presumably penta-coordinated basing on its analysis, i.r. spectra and similar nature of electronic spectra. However, X-ray crystal structure study is desirable to ascertain its preferred stereochemistry, though the compound $[\text{Cu}(\text{ac.ac})_2\text{Q}]$ has a square pyramidal structure from X-ray study.

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